

Irreversibility Analysis of Steady MHD Thermally Convective Heat Transfer of the Ethylene Glycol-Based Ternary Hybrid (Cu+SiO₂ +TiO₂) Nanofluid Flow past a Stretching Sheet with Partial Slip and Activation Energy

J. Siva Shankara Rao*¹, K. Sree Ranga Vani² and Pudi Srinivasa Rao³

¹Department of Mathematics, Government College (A), Anantapur (Dist), Andhra Pradesh, India

² Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Sri Sathya Sai Institute of Higher Learning, Anantapur, A.P., India.

³Department of Physics, Kakatiya Institute of Technology & Science (KITS), Warangal-506015, Telangana, India.

Received: Aug 23, 2025

Accepted: Sep 23, 2025

Published: Oct 03, 2025

Abstract

Nanofluids may improve heat exchange-critical functions. Pharmaceutical production, microelectronics, vehicle cooling systems, and residential refrigeration might benefit from such advancements. The study examines the convective flow of Cu+SiO₂ +TiO₂ /Ethylene glycol ternary nanofluid across a stretched sheet using varying transport characteristics, thermal radiation, and heat source effects. Oberbeck-Boussinesq approximation is used for flow equations. A fourth-order Runge-Kutta numerical approach has been added to the shooting method to solve the resulting system of interconnected, non-linear PDEs. Systematic analysis has studied how critical factors affect nanoparticle velocity, temperature profiles, and nanoconcentration. Nanoparticle volume fraction, viscosity parameter, suction, and slip impacts enhance fluid velocity, largely due to momentum boundary layer expansion. Larger Prandtl numbers increase thermal boundary layer thickness, which is important in thermal system design, but excessive thermal radiation, may reduce cooling efficiency. Prandtl number, temperature ratio difference, and mass transference parameter reduce entropy formation, improving system efficiency.

Keywords: Stretching surface, Magnetic field, Dissipation, Heat surfaces, Nanofluid, Thermal Radiation, Radiation Absorption, Activation energy.

INTRODUCTION:

Transport of a fluid subject to stretching surface has significant practical applications related to extrusion, melt spin, fibre coating, plastic and rubber sheet manufacturing. Choi (1995) came up with the term nanofluid. Nanofluids are fluids which are noted to have small volumetric content of nanometer sized particles also known as nanoparticles. Metals such as Copper, aluminium, gold, titanium, and iron as well as their oxides are used typically to make particles of this type. Fluids such as water, oil, ethylene-glycol, toluene and more serve as common base fluids. Boundary layer flow on a thermally conducting fluid has applications which include thermal management of computers, electronic devices, fans, emergency shutdown of nuclear reactors as well as in the fabrication of glass fibers, use of geothermal energy, thermal control of the boundary layer in aerodynamics, plasma research, food processing, etc. After this study different researchers (Grubka and Bobba (1985), Gupta and Gupta (1977), Sakiadis (1961). Investigation of heat transfer characteristics in nanofluids caught the sense of scientists in recent years.

A few years later, researchers identified that combining multiple nanosized particles in a clear base fluid enhances its thermal properties, leading to the development of what are now called "hybrid nanofluids." These fluids are particularly effective in cooling high-temperature thermal systems and are widely used in applications including solar systems, generator cooling units, transformers, and nuclear technology. Experimental studies by Jana et al. (2007) brought further insights into hybrid nanofluids. As a phenomenon, earlier reported by Suresh et al. (2011) that the heat conduction efficiency of these fluids improves significantly with an increased volume fraction of nanoparticles.

For instance, Venkateswarlu and Satya Narayana et al. (2020) examined the flow of Cu-Al₂O₃/H₂O hybrid nanofluid on the stretching sheet with permeability modulated by temperature-driven viscosity and viscous dissipation. In recent developments, a novel category of nanofluids termed "ternary hybrid nanofluids" has emerged, characterized by adding of three kinds of nanoparticles suspended in a pure fluid. To address these requirements, a trihybrid nanofluid was introduced, offering enhanced thermal characteristics. Several authors (Jafar Hassain et al. (2023), Ramesh et al. (2024)) explored the thermophysical and flow behaviour of a trihybrid nanofluid composed of TiO₂, CuO, and MgO suspended in water.

Thermal radiation is electromagnetic wave radiation emitted by a surface because of its heat. There are some other applications of thermal radiation: solar technology, nuclear plant and spacecraft aerodynamics, etc. The role of radiation effect on the behaviour of fluids is of great interest to many scholars and experts. Roja (2021) explored the role of thermal radiation in modifying the magneto hydrodynamic flow characteristics of Powell–Eyring C71500-Ti₆Al₄V/C₂H₆O₂-H₂O, reporting that a rise in radiation enhanced entropy generation while decaying the fluid temperature. Rashad et al. (2022), Ashwinkumar et al (2021) have looked into different types of MHD Powell–Eyring like Cu-Fe₃O₄/EG, Cu/H₂O, GO/H₂O, MHD Al₂O₃-Ag/H₂O, CuO-Al₂O₃/H₂O, MoS₂-ZnO/EG inside a permeable structure.

The applications of chemical reactions are very crucial in the food processes, fibre insulation products, fog generation, geothermal reservoirs, hydrometallurgical-based products, and nuclear reactor cooling among others. Some chemical reactions proceed at an imperceptibly slow rate or not proceed at all unless a catalyst is present. Therefore, a certain level of energy, which is called activation energy is required to set off a chemical reaction. The activation energy plays a key role of accelerating the rate of various chemical processes. Zaib et al. [29] examined the influence of nonlinear thermal radiation on stagnation point boundary layer flow over a nonlinearly stretching surface in the presence of a Carreau nanofluid. In the analysis of mass transfer, they thought about activation energy and binary reactions in chemicals. The solution of the MHD mixed convective nanofluid flow upon a vertically stretching surface was performed by Mustafa et al. (2017). The studies [Bhatti et al.(2021), Ijaz et al.(2020), Jabeen et al.,(2023)] contain some recent work that relates to the different investigations carried out on activation energy.

Mukhopadhyay (2011) studied unsteady mixed convection flow past a stretching sheet in the light of combined slip and suction/blowing. A similarity solution to an unsteady two-dimensional fluid flow which was affected with a first order chemical reaction was later generated. Vajravelu et al. (1994) numerically simulated the unsteady convective boundary layer flow of viscous fluids over a vertically stretched surface taking into account different transport properties and influence effects of thermal radiation.

Studies on nanofluids with regards to their magnetic field effects have various areas of applications especially in cooling nuclear reactor using liquid sodium, and working of induction flow meters used to measure potential difference thus generated in a fluid perpendicular to the magnetic field and flow direction (Ganesan and Palani (2004)). During

the chemotherapy process, it is reported that when localized drug targeting was not done, there was escalation of toxicities on neighbouring multiple tissues and organs but the magnetic drug targeting enables the localized drug therapeutic process. The technology lies in the premise that, the predetermined anticancer is bound to magnetic nanoparticles, which then bring the drug close to the tumour under the influence of magnets. Various researchers are keen on the usage of MHD in polymer industries and metallurgical process (Ali et al (2011), Ishak (2010), Makinde (2012)). In most cases of fluid particle flows as well as the heat generation or absorption by the fluid and the heat radiational consequences can have significant role in modifying the nature of heat transfers.

Entropy creation is one of the most interferences that arise in the thermodynamical system, which is connected with the thermodynamics' second law. In real-life situations, when a system is put into operation, then one cannot say that the system is in optimal state whereby no loss of energy as heat and friction. Therefore, conserving the amount of energy lost by the system is the major issue that is of most concern to many experts. The entropy analysis is presented to identify the irreversible loss that happens during a thermal procedure as well as assists to determine the disturbance that takes place inside and outside a system to derive the capacity of a system and become as successful as possible. The analytical solution to entropy creation of Cu-Al₂O₃/EG hybrid nanofluid by using a spinning channel was calculated and it was identified that the entropy generation increases when a higher magnetic field is used, since the magnetic field induces a high resistance in this situation resulting to enhance Joule heating in the region. Also, in the exploration of effects entropy and curvature of Cu-Al₂O₃ /Blood reviewed by Das et al. (2020), Sreedevi and Reddy (2021), Ghali et al. and Hayat et al. (2022).

This paper presents a study on the convective flow of a ternary nanofluid over a stretching surface, considering variable fluid properties and the effects of thermal radiation induced by a heat source. With the use of fourth-order Runge-Kutta method combined with shooting method, the governing nonlinear partial differential equations are solved under the Oberbeck-Boussinesq approximation. The impact of the main physical parameters on the properties of the fluid is logically examined and described.

Applications:

The current analysis brings notable observations into a comprehensive set of sectors including thermal engineering, nanotechnology, and fluid dynamics. Its discoveries offer practical applications in enhancing heat transfer operations across various industries like nuclear power generation, aerospace technology, microfluidics, and manufacturing. Moreover, the integration of dissipation, activation energy and radiative influences in trihybrid nanofluid flow models introduces a fresh perspective to comprehending heat transfer mechanisms, opening doors to new developments in associated research domains. Figure 1 illustrates various industrial applications associated with trihybrid nanofluids.

Novelty

The novelty of the present research lies in the exploration of the magneto-radiative Cu+SiO₂+TiO₂/EG ternary nanofluid flow on a stretching surface, considering activation energy and viscous dissipation phenomena.

Figure 1. Various applications associated with trihybrid nanofluids

Nomenclature:

u, v : velocity components along the cartesian x, y axes	B^* : Strength of the externally applied magnetic field
Nu : Nusselt number indicating heat transfer rate	Q : heat generation parameter
C_p : specific heat of the fluid at constant pressure	Pr : Prandtl number
B : Dynamic - viscosity related parameter,	M : Dimensionless magnetic field parameter
k_p : porous medium permeability parameter	G : buoyancy force parameter,
S : Wall Slip parameter,	E_1 : Activation energy parameter,
fw : suction parameter	δ : temperature difference parameter
T : Fluid temperature at any point	Bi : Biot number
T_∞ : Temperature of the ambient fluid far from the sheet	T_w : surface temperature of the sheet
C_w : concentration at the sheet	C : Nanoparticle concentration within the fluid
σ : electrical conductivity of the fluid	σ^* : Stefan-Boltzmann constant for thermal radiation
ρ : fluid density	k : thermal conductivity of the fluid
Q_1^1 : the radiation absorption coefficient,	β : thermal expansion coefficient
kc : chemical reaction rate coefficient	q_r : heat transfer due to thermal radiation
$D^{-1} = K$: the inverse Darcy parameter	D_B : the molecular viscosity
Ec : Eckert number representing viscous dissipation effects	f_s : Forchheimer parameter,
Sc : the Schmidt number,	Rd : Thermal radiation parameter
C_f : skin friction coefficient,	γ : the chemical reaction parameter
Sh_x : Local Sherwood number	Nu_x : Local Nusselt number,
ϕ_1 : Volume fraction of copper nanoparticles in the fluid	Br : Brinkmann number
ϕ_2 : Volume fraction of silicon oxide nanoparticles in the fluid	λ : nanoparticle mass transfer parameter
ϕ_3 : volume fraction of titanium dioxide nanoparticles in the fluid	$()_{s1}$: property of copper particles
C_∞ : Concentration of the fluid for away from the sheet	$()_{s2}$: property of silicon dioxide particles

nf : nanofluid	$(\)_{s,3}$: property of titanium dioxide particles
hnf : hybrid nanofluid	f : fluid
Be : Bejan number	$thnf$: ternary hybrid nanofluid
β_R : the mean absorption coefficient.	λ : mass transfer coefficient

MODELLING OF THE PROBLEM

We investigate a laminar, two-dimensional, steady-state flow of a ternary nanofluid prepared with ethylene glycol and nanoparticles of copper (Cu), silicon dioxide (SiO₂) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) over a stretching sheet. The sheet lies in the plane $y=0$, and the flow develops in the half-space above it. A Cartesian coordinate system is employed, where the origin is located at the leading edge of the sheet. The x-axis runs along the direction of sheet stretching (upward along the surface), while the y-axis is oriented perpendicular to the sheet, extending vertically into the nanofluid region. This setup is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Physical system and geometry of the problem

Fig.3. Synthesis setup of Tri-hybrid nanofluid preparation
Tri-hybrid nanofluid constituents

Fig.4.

Governing equations:

We assume that a constant magnetic field intensity of B^* is applied along the positive y - axis. The temperature and the concentration of the nanoparticles are maintained at fixed values T_w and C_w on the sheet whereas the ambient fluid far from the sheet has characterised by uniform values T_∞ and C_∞ respectively. The nanofluid is considered to be isotropic, homogeneous, and to possess constant electrical conductivity. Subject to these conditions and employing Boussinesq approximation, the boundary-assisted layer equations describing this MHD flow, heat transfer and mass transfer of nanofluids under Roseland approximation can be formulated as follows Ramesh et al.(2024):

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$(\rho)_{thnf} \left(u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\mu_{thnf} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) + (\rho\beta)_{thnf} g(T - T_\infty) - \left(\frac{\mu_{thnf}}{k_p} \right) u - \sigma_{thnf} B^{*2} (u) - \frac{C_b}{\sqrt{k_p}} (u^2) \quad (2)$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{thnf} \left(u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = k_{thnf} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) + Q_H (T - T_\infty) + 2\mu_{thnf} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] + \sigma_{thnf} B^{*2} (u^2) + Q_1 (C - C_\infty) + \frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3\beta_R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\left(u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) = D_B \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} \right) - k_c (C - C_\infty) \left(\frac{T}{T_\infty} \right)^n \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{E_a}{KT} \right) \quad (4)$$

The nanofluid's dynamic viscosity is assumed to be temperature dependent, which is as follows:

$$\mu_f = \mu_o \text{Exp}(m(T_o - T)) \quad (5)$$

where T_o is an ambient temperature at which nanofluid viscosity is μ_o and m is the viscosity variation parameter.

Boundary conditions:

$$u = U(x) + L \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}, v = V_w(x), -k_{thnf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h_1(T_w - T), C = C_w \text{ at } y = 0$$

(6)

$$u = 0, T = T_\infty, C = C_\infty \text{ for } y \rightarrow \infty$$

$v_w(x) = -\left(\frac{\nu U_w}{x} \right)^{1/2} f(0)$ stands for the transfer of mass near the sheet where $v_w > 0$ for suction and $v_w < 0$ for injection. The stretch on the sheet causes the flow, which moves within its own plane at a velocity directly proportional to the distance from the origin. The velocity of stretch is $U_w(x) = ax$, where a is a positive constant rate of the stretch with units inverse time (time^{-1}).

Thermo physical Properties

The properties associated with the thermal and physical behavior of nanoparticles when joined with Ethylene Glycol as the primary medium are presented in **Table.1**

The characteristics of standard and innovative nanofluids, encompassing viscosity, density, heat capacity, thermal expansion rate, thermal as well as electrical conductivities are outlined in subsequent manner

Ternary nanofluid

$$\mu_{thnf} = \frac{\mu_f}{[(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_2)(1-\phi_3)]^{2.5}}, \rho_{thnf} = \rho_f [(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_{s_1} + \frac{\rho_{s_1}}{\rho_f} \phi_1) + \frac{\rho_{s_2}}{\rho_f} \phi_2] + \frac{\rho_{s_3}}{\rho_f} \phi_3,$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{thnf} = (\rho C_p)_f (1-\phi_3) [(1-\phi_2)(1-\phi_1 + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_1}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_1) + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_2}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_2] + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_3}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_3,$$

$$\beta_{thnf} = \beta_f [(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_{s_1} + \frac{\beta_{s_1}}{\beta_f} \phi_1) + \frac{\beta_{s_2}}{\beta_f} \phi_2] + \frac{\beta_{s_3}}{\beta_f} \phi_3, \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_{hmf}} = \frac{k_{s_3} + 2k_{hmf} - 2\phi_3(k_{hmf} - k_{s_3})}{k_{s_3} + 2k_{hmf} + \phi_3(k_{hmf} - k_{s_3})},$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_{hmf}} = \frac{\sigma_{s_3} + 2\sigma_{hmf} - 2\phi_3(\sigma_{hmf} - \sigma_{s_3})}{\sigma_{s_3} + 2\sigma_{hmf} + \phi_3(\sigma_{hmf} - \sigma_{s_3})}$$

Hybrid nanofluid

$$\mu_{hnf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi_1-\phi_2+\phi_1\phi_2)^{2.5}}, \rho_{hnf} = \rho_f [(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_{s_1}) + \phi_1(1-\phi_2)\rho_{s_1}] + \phi_1\phi_2\rho_{s_2},$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{hnf} = (\rho C_p)_f [(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_{s_1}) + \phi_1(1-\phi_2)(\rho C_p)_{s_1}] + \phi_2(\rho C_p)_{s_2},$$

$$\beta_{hnf} = \beta_f [(1-\phi_1)(1-\phi_{s_1}) + \phi_1(1-\phi_2)\beta_{s_1}] + \phi_1\phi_2\beta_{s_2},$$

$$\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_{nf}} = \frac{k_{s_2} + 2k_{nf} - 2\phi_2(k_{nf} - k_{s_2})}{k_{s_2} + 2k_{nf} + \phi_2(k_{nf} - k_{s_2})}, \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_{nf}} = \frac{\sigma_{s_2} + 2\sigma_{nf} - 2\phi_2(\sigma_{nf} - \sigma_{s_2})}{\sigma_{s_2} + 2\sigma_{nf} + \phi_2(\sigma_{nf} - \sigma_{s_2})}$$

Mono nanofluid

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi_1)^{2.5}}, \rho_{nf} = \rho_f [(1-\phi_1) + \phi_1\rho_{s_1}], (\rho C_p)_{nf} = (\rho C_p)_f [(1-\phi_1) + \phi_1\rho_{s_1}],$$

$$\beta_{nf} = \beta_f [(1-\phi_1) + \phi_1\beta_{s_1}], \frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_{s_1} + 2k_f - 2\phi_1(k_f - k_{s_1})}{k_{s_1} + 2k_f + \phi_1(k_f - k_{s_1})}, \frac{\sigma_{nf}}{\sigma_f} = \frac{\sigma_{s_1} + 2\sigma_f - 2\phi_1(\sigma_f - \sigma_{s_1})}{\sigma_{s_1} + 2\sigma_f + \phi_1(\sigma_f - \sigma_{s_1})}$$

Table.1 Physical properties of nanoparticles

Physical properties	Fluid phase (Ethylene Glycol)	Copper(Cu)	SiO ₂ (Silicon Oxide)	TiO ₂ (Titanium oxide)
C _p (j/kg K)	2430	385	703	696.2
ρ (kg/ m ³)	1115	8933	2200	4250
K (W/m K)	0.253	401	1.2	8.9538
βx10 ⁻⁵	5.7	1.67	0.0565	0.90
{1/k}	0.05	0.0	0.05	0.2
φ	10.7 x 10 ⁻⁵	5.96 x 10 ⁻⁷	1.0 x 10 ⁻¹⁰	6.3 x 10 ⁻⁶
σ (S/m)				

Similarity transformations:

By taking below mentioned similarity transformations, the flow variables are obtained

$$\eta = y \left(\sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu}} \right), u = (ax) f'(\eta), v = - \left(\sqrt{av} \right) f(\eta) \tag{7}$$

Corresponding Non-dimensional governing equations:

Putting equations (7) into equations (2), (3), and (4),

$$(f''' - Bf''\theta' - D^{-1}f') - e^{B\theta} [A_1A_2[f'^2 - ff''] + A_1A_3G\theta - A_1A_6M^2(f') - A_1fs(f'^2)] = 0 \tag{8}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} &A_1(A_5 + \frac{4Rd}{3})\theta'' + A_1A_4Pr(f'\theta' - 2f'\theta) + A_1PrQ\theta + \\ &+ EcPr e^{-B\theta}(f'')^2 + A_1A_6EcPrM^2(f')^2 + PrQ_1\varphi = 0 \end{aligned} \right| \tag{9}$$

$$\Phi'' + Sc(f\Phi' - 2f'\Phi - Sc\gamma\varphi(1 + n\delta\theta) \text{Exp}(-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta\theta})) = 0 \tag{10}$$

Corresponding Non-dimensional boundary conditions:

The transformed boundary conditions are

$$f'(0) = 1 + Sf''(0), f(0) = f_w, \theta' = -Bi(1 - \theta(0)), \Phi(0) = 1 \text{ at } \eta = 0 \tag{11}$$

$$f'(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \Phi(\infty) \rightarrow 0 \tag{12}$$

Where $fw = \frac{v_w}{\sqrt{av}}$, suction represents for $f_w > 0$, whereas injection indicates for $f_w < 0$ at the surface.

$$B = -m(T_w - T_\infty), M^2 = \frac{\sigma B_0^2}{\rho a}, G = \frac{\beta g(T_w - T_\infty)}{U_w v_w^2}, Pr = \frac{\mu C_p}{k_f},$$

$$fs = \frac{Cb}{\sqrt{k_p}} x, Q = \frac{v Q_H}{(\rho C_p)_f v_w^2}, Ec = \frac{U_w^2}{C_p(T_w - T_\infty)}, Q_1 = \frac{v Q_1^1}{(\rho C_p)_f v_w^2},$$

$$Sc = \frac{v}{D_B}, Rd = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{\beta_R k_f}, \gamma = \frac{k_c v}{v_w^2}, B_i = \frac{h_f}{k_f} \left(\frac{v}{a}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, S = L \left(\frac{a}{v}\right)^{1/2}, E_1 = \frac{E_a}{KT_\infty},$$

$$\theta_w = \frac{T_w}{T_\infty}, \delta = (\theta_w - 1).$$

$$A_1 = (1 - \phi_1)(1 - \phi_2)(1 - \phi_3)^{2.5}, A_2 = [(1 - \phi_1)(1 - \phi_{s_1} + \frac{\rho_{s_1}}{\rho_f} \phi_1) + \frac{\rho_{s_2}}{\rho_f} \phi_2] + \frac{\rho_{s_3}}{\rho_f} \phi_3$$

$$A_3 = [(1 - \phi_1)(1 - \phi_{s_1} + \frac{\beta_{s_1}}{\beta_f} \phi_1) + \frac{\beta_{s_2}}{\beta_f} \phi_2] + \frac{\beta_{s_3}}{\beta_f} \phi_3$$

$$A_4 = (1 - \phi_3) \left[(1 - \phi_2)(1 - \phi_1 + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_1}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_1) + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_2}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_2 \right] + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s_3}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \phi_3$$

$$A_5 = \frac{k_{s_3} + 2k_{hmf} - 2\phi_3(k_{hmf} - k_{s_3})}{k_{s_3} + 2k_{hmf} + \phi_3(k_{hmf} - k_{s_3})}, A_6 = \frac{\sigma_{s_3} + 2\sigma_{hmf} - 2\phi_3(\sigma_{hmf} - \sigma_{s_3})}{\sigma_{s_3} + 2\sigma_{hmf} + \phi_3(\sigma_{hmf} - \sigma_{s_3})}$$

SKIN FRICTION COEFFICIENT, NUSSELT NUMBER AND SHERWOOD NUMBER

The skin friction coefficient (C_f), local Nusselt number (Nu_x), local Sherwood number (Sh_x) tend to have the following definitions. $\left(\frac{1}{2} C_f\right) \sqrt{Re_x} = f''(0)$, $Nu_x (Re_x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 1/\theta(0)$, $Sh_x (Re_x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 1/\Phi(0)$ Where Re_x indicates local Reynolds number.

ENTROPY GENERATION:

Over the last several years, the focus of researchers and engineers has been on reducing the loss of precious energy, especially in thermodynamic systems where energy loss may have a major impact in the performance of systems. In viscous, incompressible, and electrically conducting fluids in magneto hydrodynamic flows, irreversibility can be evaluated by entropy generation. Based on work of Woods, the local volumetric rate at which entropy creation happens in such a fluid with the assistance of magnetic field takes the form

$$S'' = \frac{1}{T_\infty^2} \left(k_{hmf} + \frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3\beta_R} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{\mu_{hmf}}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{hmf} B_o^2}{T_\infty} (u^2) + \frac{D_B}{\Delta C} \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{D_B}{\Delta T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}\right) \right)$$

The first term describes an effect of the irreversibility under the process of the temperature transfer, the second one ascribes the effect of the entropy creation under the viscous dissipation process, the third one accounts the effect of the magnetic field, which is often called as Joule heating, and the last one is the effect of the entropy generation under the process of the nanoparticles' mass transfer and their complex behaviour in the base fluid.

In non-dimensional form

$$N_s = \frac{a^2 S''}{k_f} = (1 + Rd) \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + \frac{Br}{\Omega} \left[e^{-B\theta} \left(\frac{\partial f'}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + M^2 A_6 (f')^2 \right] + \lambda \left[\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \eta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right) \right]$$

where $Br = Ec Pr$ (Brinkmann number)

$$\lambda = \frac{C_0 D_B}{k_f} \text{ (nanoparticles mass transfer parameter)}$$

Let $N_1 = (1 + Rd) \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 \rightarrow$ heat transfer driven entropy generation,

$N_2 = \frac{Br}{\Omega} \left[e^{-B\theta} \left(\frac{\partial f'}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + M^2 A_6 (f')^2 \right] \rightarrow$ entropy generation caused by friction along with

magnetic field,

$N_3 = \lambda \left[\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \eta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right) \right] \rightarrow$ entropy creation due to mass diffusion

Then, we have $N_s = N_1 + N_2 + N_3$

The ratio of entropy generation as a result of heat and mass transfer to the overall entropy creation is termed as the Bejan number (Be).

$$Be = \frac{1}{1 + \psi} = \frac{N_1 + N_3}{N_s}$$

where irreversibility ratio (ψ) is expressed by $\psi = \frac{N_2}{N_1 + N_3}$

The heat as well as mass transfer effects dominate when $0 \leq \psi \leq 1$, where as the friction of the fluid with the magnetic effects dominate if $\psi > 1$. Both heat transfer and fluid friction effects dominate when $\psi = 1$. Be varies between 0 and 1. When $Be = 1$, it means irreversibility is purely caused by heat transfer and mass transfer with insignificance contribution by the friction of the fluid and effects brought by magnetic field. Alternatively, $Be = 0.5$ describes a state of balance; that is, where the entropy produced by the heat transfer and mass transfer is equal to the entropy generation by fluid friction and magnetic effects. Moreover, dynamics of Be are analysed at optimum parameter values where the entropy generation is minimal.

Numerical procedure

The velocity equation (11), temperature equation (12), and concentration equation (13) along with the associated conditions (14 and 15) are resolved, employing the RKF-45 method in conjunction with shooting technique. These equations, being higher-order with two-point boundary conditions, are structured into a set of initial value problems of first-order to facilitate the solution process.

We consider

$$\frac{df}{d\eta} = p, \frac{d^2 f}{d\eta^2} = \frac{dp}{d\eta} = q, \frac{d^3 f}{d\eta^3} = \frac{dq}{d\eta} = r, \frac{d\theta}{d\eta} = p_1, \frac{d^2 \theta}{d\eta^2} = \frac{dp_1}{d\eta} = q_1, \frac{d\Phi}{d\eta} = p_2, \frac{d^2 \Phi}{d\eta^2} = \frac{dp_2}{d\eta} = q_2$$

$$(r - Bqp_1 - D^{-1}p) - e^{B\theta} A_1 A_2 (p^2 - fq) + A_1 A_3 G\theta - A_1 A_6 M^2 p - A_1 f_s p^2 = 0$$

(16)

$$A_1 \left[A_5 + \frac{4}{3} R_d \right] q_1 + A_1 A_4 P_r [fp_1 - 2p\theta] + A_1 P_r Q\theta + E_c P_r e^{-B\theta} q^2 + A_1 A_6 P_r M^2 E_c p^2 + P_r Q_1 \Phi = 0$$

(17)

$$q_2 + S_c [fp_2 - 2p\Phi] - S_c \gamma \Phi (1 + n \delta \theta) \text{Exp}\left\{-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta \theta}\right\} = 0 \quad (18)$$

With

$$p = 1 + S_q, f = f_w, p_1 = -\frac{B_i}{A_s} (1 - \theta), \Phi(0) = 1 \text{ at } \eta = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$p \rightarrow 0, \theta \rightarrow 0, \Phi \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty$$

Shooting method is used to solve initial value problem by estimating the missing values after selecting the appropriate parameters. A step size of 0.1 is used for the calculations, with an error tolerance of approximately 10^{-6} .

MATHEMATICA CODE VALIDATION

The methods and techniques used here were authenticated by cross-examining the conclusions drawn from the current research with those already published. The Table 2 and 3 give the coherence of the present investigation. It can be seen that on restricting certain parametric values, results of the present work will coincide with that of Chandrakala and Srinivasa Rao [4] and Ramesh et al. [20].

Table2: Validation of current solutions with those of Chandrakala and Srinivasa Rao (2025) for R=m=A=E1=δ=n=0 for Nu and Sh at η=0

G	M	Q	fs	R _d	Ec	φ	A	Bi	Sc	γ	Chandrakala & Srinivasa Rao results(2025)		Present results	
											Nu(0)	Sh(0)	Nu(0)	Sh(0)
2	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.05	0.01	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.0745348	1.10843	0.0745460	1.10854
4											0.0748758	1.11052	0.0748628	1.11052
6											0.0742124	1.10692	0.0742131	1.10701
	1.0										0.073889	1.10484	0.073891	1.10482
	1.5										0.0745928	1.10904	0.0745924	1.10912
		1.0									0.0752126	1.11082	0.0752125	1.11095
		1.5									0.1268788	1.126754	0.1268791	1.126724
			0.3								0.131249	1.142482	0.131222	1.142483
			0.5								0.0830168	1.10643	0.0830142	1.10644
				1.5							0.094189	1.09843	0.094171	1.09847
				5.0							0.0627972	1.09678	0.0627968	1.09644
					0.1						0.05986	1.0798	0.05986	1.0798

G	M	Q	fs	R _d	Ec	φ	A	Bi	Sc	γ	Chandrakala & Srinivasa Rao results(2025)		Present results	
											Nu(0)	Sh(0)	Nu(0)	Sh(0)
											5	45	1	61
					0.1						0.08480	1.1058	0.08480	1.1056
					5						28	9	22	1
						0.0					0.08814	1.0986	0.08813	1.0982
						3					9	7	7	4
						0.0					0.09010	1.0680	0.09010	1.0681
						5					11	9	12	8
							0.				0.09142	1.0492	0.09142	1.0492
							2				8	5	4	1
							0.				0.19339	1.1084	0.19340	1.1084
							3				7	32	3	36
								0.			0.21488	1.1204	0.21489	1.1204
								4			9	2	1	5
								0.			0.21489	1.3296	0.21489	1.3297
								6			2	8	4	2
									0.6		0.08324	1.3410	0.08324	1.3411
									6		27	9	35	2
										1.3	0.08812	1.1245	0.08812	1.1245
										3	9	6	4	4
										1.	0.09141	1.1389	0.09141	1.1384
										0	25	6	21	5
										1.	0.10891	1.1462	0.10891	1.1462
										5	2	1	1	8

Table3: $-\theta'(0)$ values are compared for varying Pr while neglecting mass transfer ($Sc = \gamma = E_1 = \delta = 0$) and $K = M = fs = Ec = Rd = Q_1 = 0$.

Pr	Ramesh et al.(2024)	Present results
0.72	0.808834161254604	0.8088343
1	1.0000083736533	1.0000081
3	1.92367866800503	1.9236793
10	3.72067116817853	3.7206715

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 6 to 13 show how key variables affect velocity, temperature, and nanoconcentration. The parameter values adapted for this investigation include: $\phi = 0.01$, $G = 2$, $M = 0.5$, $K = 0.2$, $fs = 0.1$, $B = 0.2$, $Q = 0.5$, $Rd = 0.5$, $Ec = 0.05$, $fw = 0.1$, $S = 0.2$, $Pr = 1.71$, $E_1 = 0.1$, $Sc = 0.2$, $\gamma = 0.5$, $\delta = 0.2$, $Bi = 0.2$ This work explores how these parameters influence the flow, the temperature as well as the concentration distributions inside the ternary nanofluid system under the given conditions.

Analysis of the fluid velocity

The velocity distribution (f') considering diverse parameters is exhibited in figs.(6a-6h). Fig.6a demonstrates the velocity with ϕ . The fluid's boundary layer thickness grows on par with increase in ϕ , and hence augments f' . Fig.6b exhibits variation of f' with G .

Increase G depreciates the f' in three kinds of nanofluids. From fig.6c an observation is made that f' decays when M enhances. However, among the three, the ternary nanofluid demonstrates the highest velocity profile. Fig.6d demonstrates the variation of f' with K in EG based ternary nanofluids($\text{Cu}+\text{SiO}_2+\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$). The velocity profiles show that velocity distribution reduces as the inverse Darcy parameter, K , increases because it has an inverse relation with the porous medium permeability, thereby as amplification in K , the permeability decreases hence the fluid velocity slows down. Fig.6e exhibits f' with Forchheimer parameter (f_s). A rise in Forchheimer parameter(f_s) enhances the resistance to the flow and hence, causing a decline in f' . When $f_s = 0$, the flow corresponds to the Darcian regime, where the velocity in the flow is maximum due to the total absence of inertial drag. Fig.6f exhibits the variation of f' with respect to B . We identify from the graph that larger the B higher the nanofluid velocity. Also, values of velocity in Trihybrid nanofluid are superior to those of remaining nanofluids. The velocity distribution in the flow enlarges as f_w is augmented as shown in Fig.6g.

Figure.6 (a-h): f' with ϕ , G , M , K , f_s , B

Analysis of the fluid temperature

The distribution temperature (θ) with various parameters is exhibited in figs.(7a-7f). θ augments with rise in ϕ (Fig. 7a). An augmentation in ϕ elevates the nanofluid's effective thermal conductivity, which consequently intensifies both conduction and convection heat transfer mechanisms. The heat transfer efficiency of the fluid improves as increase in thermal conductivity. Consequently, the use of nanofluids significantly influences temperature distribution and proves beneficial in thermal management applications. Hybrid and ternary nanofluids exhibit superior thermal distribution compared to mono nanofluids. An upward trend in the temperature profile θ is noted in Figure 7c with increasing values of Q as a result of the extra supply of the thermal energy to the fluid. Also, the temperature distribution rises incessantly due to convection. As a result of this phenomenon, the temperature of the boundary layer increases which results in the thickening of the thermal boundary layer. It is identified that the temperature of the nanofluids escalates by a large percentage compared to the normal fluid during elevated values of Q . Figs.7d demonstrates the variation of θ with R_d in THNF, HNF and MNF cases. It is observed from the profile that an enhancement in R_d causes the temperature in the flow domain to rise. Therefore, it is evident that with the aim of speed up the cooling procedure, minimizing the thermal radiation is necessary. The control of E_c on θ can be explored in fig.7e. The profile shows that higher the dissipation larger the temperature in the flow system. This phenomenon is attributed to the growth in thermal boundary layer thickness associated with increased dissipative energy.

The impact of P_r over θ can be observed in fig. 7f. The profiles explore that distribution of the temperature in the fluid augments as the P_r is enhanced. As the P_r is raised, the thermal boundary layer is expanded in the fluid region that in turn contributes to the increase of thermal distribution throughout the flowing fluid. Compared to hybrid and mono nanofluids, ternary hybrid nanofluids demonstrate a relatively higher temperature dispersion, while the mass dispersion in THNF is comparatively lower than that of HNF and MNF. Fig.7g expresses the stimulation of Bi on temperature. The distribution of the temperature grows as the Bi rises. This is because a growth in Bi causes to increase in temperature, primarily due to the increased heat transfer from the Biot boundary to the adjacent fluid region. Fig.7h. Explores the Q_1 effect on the profile of temperature. As Q_1 increases the effective thermal diffusivity grows. Consequently, the temperature profile enhances.

Figure.7 (a-h): θ with ϕ , Q , Rd , Ec , Pr , Bi , Q_1

Analysis of the fluid nanoconcentration (Φ)

The concentration distribution (Φ) with diverse parameters is exhibited in figs.(8a-8d). The profiles show that both heat and mass dispersion are significantly higher in the ternary nanofluid evaluated against hybrid and mono nanofluids. The impact of S_c over the nanoconcentration can be observed in fig.8a. The profiles reveal that the Φ gets smaller with increasing S_c . The Φ upsurges in ternary nanofluid and decays in rest of the nanofluids with an increase in chemical reaction case ($\gamma > 0$) (fig.8b). Fig. 8c illustrates that an enhancement in E_1 causes to a higher concentration in flow domain. This is because the solutal boundary layer thickens as the E_1 increases. Fig. 8d explores that the Φ grows in ternary nanofluid and depreciates in rest of the nanofluids as an increase in temperature difference ratio (δ).

Figure.8 (a-d): Variation of Nanoconcentration(C) with Sc, γ , E_1 , δ

Entropy generation (Ns) trends in fluid flow

Entropy generation trends are explored in Figs.(9a-9k). The fluctuation of N_s with G is established in Fig.9a. Increase in G augments N_s significantly in the vicinity of the wall and its variation is negligibly small farther away from the sheet. The fig 8b shows the dependency of N_s on M . The entropy production rate grows close to the sheet with M , whereas Minimal variation in entropy generation is detected which is at a greater distance to the sheet. It discloses that besides fluid friction and heat as well as mass transfer, the magnetic field is also a considerable entropy generator. A peak in entropy production is also noted at the stretching surface and in its immediate vicinity. Consequently, in order to observe a reduction in entropy generation throughout the boundary layer region, it is important to mitigate the magnetic parameter which is a value of an interest that is significant in the nuclear MHD propulsion mechanism applications. The entropy generation (N_s) grows with viscosity parameter (B)(Fig.8c) and decays with R_d (Fig.8e) in the vicinity of the stretching surface while its effect is insignificant in the region farther away from the wall. Fig. 8d reveals that N_s enhances when Q augments. Higher the energy dissipation- E_c , larger the entropy creation in the nanofluid (fig. 8f). Thus viscosity control plays a vital role in lubricating systems and oil cooling processes, because it determines the fluid flow characteristics and facilitates effective thermal management. From fig. 8h it is noted that N_s decays with higher values of B_i . Fig. 8i shows that N_s grows as E_1 grows, especially in surroundings of the stretching surface. In contrast, fig. 8j reveals that the entropy generation diminishes for higher values of temperature difference ratio (δ) near the surface, with insignificant effects at greater distances from the surface. Fig. 8k demonstrates that Entropy generation (N_s) near the surface declines with increasing mass transfer parameter (λ) with little effect far away from the surface. This kind of behaviour suggests that enhanced mass transfer leads to reduced entropy generation, thereby improving thermodynamic efficiency farther from the stretching sheet. The implication of Br on N_s is shown in fig. 8l. Br exerts a positive influence on entropy generation. As Br augments, N_s increases.

Figure.9 (a-b): N_s with G, M, B

Figure.9 (d-f): N_s with Q, R_d, E_c

Fig.9g-9i: Entropy Generation (N_s) with Bi, E_1, δ

Fig.9j-9k: Entropy Generation (N_s) with λ, Br

Fig.10a-10c: Bejan Number (Be) variations with G, M, B

Fig.10d-10f: Bejan Number (Be) variations with Q, Rd, Ec

Bejan number (Be) trends in fluid flow:

To see whether the heat as well as mass transfer entropy creation is predominant against those generated by fluid friction and influence of a magnetic field, plots of Be against various values of parameters (Figs. 10a -10l) are taken. Fig. 10b shows that Be decreases when M enhances. For larger M, entropy generation resulting from viscous dissipation and magnetic field becomes negligible measured against to the irreversibilities arising from heat and mass exchange in the boundary layer adjacent to the stretching sheet. It is seen from Figs. 10c, 10d,10h, and 10i that Be decays when the viscosity parameter (B)/ heat generation parameter Q/Biot number(Bi)/activation energy (E1) enhances. It is inferred that the contributions of fluid friction and magnetic field effects to entropy production outweighs that owing to heat and mass transfer near the surface when B/Q/Bi/E1 grows. For an increase in G/Ec, entropy generation arises from frictional and magnetic irreversibilities outweigh those due to the heat and mass transfer near the stretching sheet (Figs. 10a & 10f). Hence Be decreases near the wall. As Rd is increased, heat and mass transfer irreversibility becomes dominant over that caused by viscous dissipation and magnetic field effects (Fig.10e). A reverse effect has been observed in case of B (fig.10c). Fig.(10j) explores that Be experiences enhancement with rising values of δ (Temperature difference ratio).

Fig. 10k represents the Bejan number (Be) with nanoparticle mass transfer parameter (λ). From the profiles the analysis reveals that with increasing λ, the entropy creation associated with heat as well as mass transfer becomes more significant than that arising from frictional and magnetic irreversibilities. Fig. 10l shows that the Bejan number Be reduces as Br(Ω⁻¹) increases. This observation is justified as the magnitude of irreversibility associated with viscous dissipation and the magnetic forces can be enhanced by higher Br(Ω⁻¹), having zero impact on the irreversibility caused by heat as well as mass transfer leading to increase in ψ and a decrease in Be. To do entropy analysis, the group parameter is very crucial. It analyses the comparative significance of the fluid friction effects concerning that of the temperature gradient entropy generation.

Analysis of surface drag, Nusselt and Sherwood numbers (Fig.11, Fig.12, Fig.13)

Surface drag ($C_{f,R_{ex}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$), heat transfer and mass transfer rates ($Nu_x R_{ex}^{-1/2}, Sh_x R_{ex}^{-1/2}$) over the surface (η=0) are exhibited under different parametric conditions of G,M,Rd,Ec, Q, B,fw,fs,E1,δ, S,Bi. The surface drag upsurges on the wall(η=0) with enhancement in G/Rd/Ec/Q/B/E1/S, while it depreciates with larger values of M/fw/fs/Bi/δ. $Nu_x R_{ex}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ rises with enhancement in fs/E1/δ/S/Bi while it reduces with higher values of G/M/Rd/ Ec/Q/B/fw upon the surface. The mass transfer rate ($Sh_x R_{ex}^{\frac{1}{2}}$) rises as increase in G/Rd/Ec/Q/B/fw/fs/ E1/δ/Bi while it reduces with higher values of M/S on the wall.

In all these variations, it is observed that these three engineering parameters on the surface in ternary nanofluid are comparatively higher than those of rest of the nanofluids.

CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive numerical simulations has been undertaken to analyse about the behaviour of a ternary nanofluid flow over a stretching surface influenced by a transverse magnetic field, variable viscosity, porous medium effects, radiation, and entropy generation. This investigation accounts for the influence of several factors such as nanoparticle volume fraction , thermal and solutal buoyancy, Forchheimer number, Biot number, activation energy and viscous dissipation, among others. The key conclusions derived from the current research can be outlined as follows:

- The fluid velocity grows with ϕ , B , fw , and S , primarily owing to the momentum boundary layer expansion. In contrast, velocity decays with M , fs , G , and Bi due to enhanced resistance forces such as Lorentz drag and inertial resistance.
- Under equivalent operating conditions, the velocity of ternary nanofluids surpasses that of mono and hybrid nanofluids.
- Within the boundary layer, the temperature is augmented by enhancing the ϕ , Ec , M , Rd , Q , Bi , $Q1$. Ternary nanofluids consistently demonstrate superior thermal performance due to enhanced thermal conductivity from the combined effects of multiple nanoparticles.
- Nanoparticle concentration decreases with Sc but increases with higher γ and $E1$, due to intensified solutal diffusion.
- The ternary nanofluid system shows improved mass dispersion compared to hybrid and mono systems, indicating better mass transport properties.
- Entropy generation is amplified by higher values of M , Q , Rd , Ec and $E1$.
- Pr , δ , and λ help reduce entropy generation, contributing to improved system efficiency.
- The Bejan number analysis reveals that heat and mass transfer irreversibilities dominate in most scenarios, except near the stretching surface for large magnetic fields or frictional parameters. This highlights the importance of managing magnetic and viscous effects to reduce entropy generation.
- Surface drag increases with higher Rd , G , Ec , and ϕ but declines with M , fw , and Bi .
- Heat transfer rate is elevated with higher λ , S , and $E1$, but is suppressed by M .

Fig.10 (g,h,i) : Bejan Number(Be) variations with Bi , $E1$, δ

Fig.10 (j,k) : Bejan Number(Be) variations with λ , Br

Fig. 11: $\tau=0$ with G&M, Rd&Ec, Q&B, fw&fs, S&Bi, E1& δ in Ternary, Hybrid and Mono Nanofluids at $\eta=0$

Fig. 12: Nusselt number (Nu) variations with G&M, Rd&Ec, Q&B, fw&fs, S&Bi, E1& δ in Ternary, Hybrid and Mono Nanofluids at $\eta=0$

Fig. 13: Variation of Sherwood number (Sh) with G & M , Rd & Ec , Q & B , fw & fs , S & Bi , $E1$ & δ in Ternary, Hybrid and Mono Nanofluids at $\eta=0$

Acknowledgements

We confirm that they helped with the idea, planning, analysis, writing, or editing of the paper. We'd also like to thank Prof.D.R.V. Prasada Rao, UGC-BSR Faculty Fellow and Retired Professor of Mathematics at Sri Krishnadevaraya University in Anantapur, A.P., India, for his valuable suggestions in the improvement of a manuscript of research paper.

Data Availability: The datasets used and analyzed during the current study available from the corresponding authors on reasonable request.

Funding : We have not received any financial aid from any agency

ORCID iD

J. Siva Shankara Rao : <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6713-128X>

Pudi Srinivasa Rao : <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2333-0718>

Sreeranga Vani : <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3464-6104>

REFERENCES

- Ali, F. M., Nazar, R., Arifin, N. M., and Pop, I., Effect of Hall current on MHD mixed convection boundary layer flow over a stretched vertical flat plate, *Meccanica* 46, 1103-1112 (2011).
- Ashwinkumar, G.P.; Samrat, S.P.; Sandeep, N. Convective heat transfer in MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over two different geometries. *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transf.* **2021**, 127, 105563.
- Bhatti, M.M., Michaelides, E.E. (2021). Study of Arrhenius activation energy on the thermobioconvection nanofluid flow over a Riga plate. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 143: 2029-2038. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-020-09492-3>
- Chandrakala, P., & Srinivasa Rao, V. (2025). Influence of dissipation and chemical reaction on heat and mass transfer in ternary nanofluids over a stretching sheet in porous media. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*, 46(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01430750.2025.2471995>
- Choi, S.U.S., Enhancing thermal conductivity of fluids with nanoparticles, *Developments and Applications of Non – Newtonian Flows*, FED – vol. 231 / MD, 66: (1995) 99 – 105.
- Das, S.; Sarkar, S.; Jana, R.N. Feature of Entropy Generation in Cu- Al_2O_3 /Ethylene Glycol Hybrid Nanofluid Flow Through a Rotating Channel. *Bionanoscience* **2020**, 10, 950–967.
- Ganesan, P., Palani, G., Finite difference analysis of unsteady natural convection MHD flow past an inclined plate with variable surface heat and mass flux, *Internal Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 47 (19 – 20) (2004) 4449 – 4457.
- Ghali, D.; Redouane, F.; Abdelhak, R.; Mahammed, A.B.; Zineb, C.D.; Jamshed, W.; Eid, M.R.; Eldin, S.M.; Musa, A.; Nasir, N.A.A.M. Mathematical Entropy Analysis of Natural Convection of MWCNT— Fe_3O_4 /Water Hybrid Nanofluid with Parallel Magnetic Field via Galerkin Finite Element Process. *Symmetry* **2022**, 14, 2312.

- Grubka, L.G., and Bobba, K. M., Heat transfer characteristics of a continuous stretching surface with variable temperature, *J. Heat Transfer – Trans. ASME* 107 (1985) 248 – 250.
- Gupta, P. S., and Gupta, A. S., Heat and Mass Transfer on a stretching sheet with suction or blowing, *Can. J. Chem, J. Eng.* 55 (1977) 744 – 746.
- Hayat, A.U.; Ullah, I.; Khan, H.; Weera, W.; Galal, A.M. Numerical Simulation of Entropy Optimization in Radiative Hybrid Nanofluid Flow in a Variable Features Darcy–Forchheimer Curved Surface. *Symmetry* **2022**, 14, 2057.
- Ijaz, M., Ayub, M., Malik, M.Y., Khan, H., Alderremy, A.A., Aly, S. (2020). Entropy analysis in nonlinearly convective flow of the Sisko model in the presence of Joule heating and activation energy: The Buongiorno model. *Physica Scripta*, 95(2): 025402. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1402-4896/ab2dc7>
- Ishak, A., Unsteady MHD flow and heat transfer in over a stretching plate, *J. Applied Sci.* 10 (18) (2010) 2127 – 2130.
- Jabeen, K., Mushtaq, M., Mushtaq, T., Muntazir, R.M.A. (2023). A numerical study of boundary layer flow of Williamson nanofluid in the presence of viscous dissipation, bioconvection, and activation energy. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10407782.2023.2187494>
- Jafar Hasnain & Nomana Abid (2023) Numerical investigation for thermal growth in water and engine oil-based ternary nanofluid using three different shaped nanoparticles over a linear and nonlinear stretching sheet, *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, 83:12,1365-1376, DOI: 10.1080/10407782.2022.2104582.
- Jana, S.; Khojin, A.S.; Zhong, W.H. Enhancement of fluid thermal conductivity by the addition of single and hybrid nano-additives. *Thermochimica* **2007**, 462, 45–55.
- Makinde, O. D., Entropy analysis for MHD boundary layer flow and heat transfer over a flat plate with a convective surface boundary condition, *Int. Journal of Energy*, 10 (2) (2012) 142 – 154.
- Mukhopadhyay, S., Heat transfer analysis of unsteady flow over a porous stretching surface embedded in a porous medium in presence of thermal radiation, *Acta Tech.* 56 (2011) 115 – 124.
- Mustafa, M., Khan, J.A., Hayat, T., Alsaedi, A. (2017). Buoyancy effects on the MHD nanofluid flow past a vertical surface with chemical reaction and activation energy. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 108: 1340-1346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2017.01.029>
- Ramesh GK, Madhukesh JK, Shehzab SA, Rauf A. Ternary nanofluid with heat source/sink and porous medium effects in stretchable convergent/divergent channel. *Proceedings of the institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*. 2024;238(1): 134-143. doi:10.1177/09544089221081344.
- Rashad, A.M.; Nafe, M.A.; Eisa, D.A. Heat Generation and Thermal Radiation Impacts on Flow of Magnetic Eyring–Powell Hybrid Nanofluid in a Porous Medium. *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, 48, 939–952.
- Roja, A. Scrutinization of entropy on MHD Eyring–Powell C71500–Ti6Al4V nanoparticles suspended in a C₂H₆O₂–H₂O hybrid base fluid with heat generation. *Heat Transf.* **2021**, 51, 193–209.
- Sakiadis, B.C., Boundary layer behavior on a continuous solid surface, *AIChE J.* 7 (1961) 26 – 28
- Sreedevi, P.; Reddy, P.S. Entropy generation and heat transfer analysis of alumina and carbon nanotubes based hybrid nanofluid inside a cavity. *Phys. Scr.* **2021**, 96, 085210.
- Suresh, S.; Venkataraj, K.P.; Selvakumar, P. Synthesis, characterization of Al₂O₃-Cu nanocomposite powder and water based nanofluids. *Adv. Mater. Res.* **2011**, 328, 1560–1567. [CrossRef] **(8)**
- Vajravelu, K., Flow and heat transfer in a saturated porous medium over a stretching surface, *Z. Angew. Math. Mech.* 74 (1994) 605 – 614.
- Vajravelu, K., Prasad, K. V., Chiu – On Ng, Unsteady convective boundary layer flow of a viscous fluid at a vertical surface with variable fluid properties, *Nonlinear Analysis: Real World Applications*, 14 (2013) 455 – 464.
- Venkateswarlu B, Satya Narayana P.V. : Cu – Al₂O₃/H₂O hybrid nanofluid flow past a porous stretching sheet due to temperature dependent viscosity and viscous dissipation. *Heat transfer*. 2020;1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hjt.21884>.
- Zaib, A., Rashidi, M.M., Chamkha, A.J., Mohammad, N.F. (2018). Impact of nonlinear thermal radiation on stagnation-point flow of a Carreau nanofluid past a nonlinear stretching sheet with binary chemical reaction and activation energy. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*, 232(6): 962-972. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954406217695847>